

Translating the expressive language devices used by Alisher Navoi in his epic poem “Farhod and Shirin”

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Key words

figurative speech, literary device, metaphor, language, word, speech, speech ethics, literary work, literary language, ghazal, epic-poem, linguistic norms, aesthetic importance

Annotatsiya

The current article represents the analysis of figurative language usage such as simile and metaphor in the works of Alisher Navoi including the epic poem “Farhod and Shirin”. The principle objective of this research work is to analyze the degree of translation of literary devices and comparing the lingua stylistic peculiarities of the source and target language. Moreover, we have looked at some literary devices that reflect the linguistic and cultural characteristics in the original text and present the greatest difficulty in translation. The solution of translation problems of lingua-cultural nature is provided by correct perception of the received information. Considering two language’s possibilities of adequacy in lexical and semantic fields we have broadly applied comparative typological methods in translation. In addition, basing on some linguists’ theories, we have made an attempt to find appropriate equivalencies of used literary devices by Navoi in the English languages.

Introduction

Alisher Navoi is known as a founder of Uzbek literary language. He composed a great number of poems, ghazals, rubais and epic poems in this language. Navoi took one of the honorable places among classics of world literature. He devoted all his activity and a deep humanistic creation to serve for the sake of common people, flourishing of the enlightenment, science, art and literature.

Respectively to the works of Makhmud Koshghari and Akhmad Yugnaki Navoi continued their work referring to study the linguistic norms of Uzbek literary language.

His creative activity in literature is seen to use variety of genres i.e 16 genres efficiently. In poems, ghazals or epic-poems his style of using the words, phrases, proverbs, and aphorisms with accuracy and delicateness serve provision of spiritual contact between the author and the reader. They directly attain to the reader’s insight of mind and the soul.

Methods and methodologies

Similes have been studied so far either from a literary viewpoint as one of the stylistic expressive means of language based on associative perception and mapping of the world. Enkvist (1973); Galperin (1977); Leech & Short (1981); Kukhareno, 1988; Esser (1993) or in the context of philosophy of language in correlation with metaphor Aristotle (1954); Black (1962); Davidson (1979); Wierzbicka (1990); Tirrel (1991); Ortony (1993); Todd & Clarke (1999); Chiappe & Kennedy (2000); Utsumi (2007), and others.

Abrams and Harpham defines simple meaning to get understanding on figurative language that is apprehending the standard meaning in order to achieve some special meaning or effect [5,118]

Lazar G. says: “All these form of figurative and metaphorical language one thing in common. In classical rhetoric, the term metaphor comes from Greek meta expressing ‘change’ and, pherein meaning ‘to carry’. Metaphors thus involve a ‘carrying across’ of

meaning from one object to another. Identification is made between two apparently dissimilar things, so that some of the characteristics of the one are 'carried over' to the other. For example, if in the dictionary a 'trickle of water' means a very small quantity of water that flows slowly, then a 'trickle of visitors' means a small number of people who arrive gradually or in small groups.[12,13].

Lazar, G. in his book *Meaning and metaphors* gives definitions to the simile and metaphor. According to him, a simile is a direct comparison between two things which resemble each other in at least one way, although they are unlike each other in many others. In a simile the words *as* and *like* are used to explicitly make the comparison, e.g. as quick as a flash: I was so tired that my brain felt like cotton wool.

Metaphor he says a comparison which identifies one thing with another, dissimilar thing. Some of the qualities of the second are transferred to the first. For example, in Shakespeare's *Romeo and Juliet*, when Romeo famously says 'Juliet is the sun' some of the qualities of the sun (warmth, radiance, etc.) are transferred to Juliet. Unlike a simile, a metaphore states that one thing is another thing, not just that one thing is like another thing [11,15]

Results

Almost in all epic-poems of "Khamssa" Navoi writes his ideas about words, language and speech. He separates special chapters under the title "A little bit about words". For instance, in the introductory part of "Layli and Majnun" he addresses directly to the word, using metaphor. He says- "You are the pearl. No, the pearl is as a drop of water comparing with you. You are the endless song that does not come to its end. You are the treasure that is not emptied if one spends over and over. You are an infinite space in dignity.

Owing to you language became honorable and wealthy". Here Navoi compares the word with unlike words like the pearl, endless song, unlimited treasure and infinite space. As a rule metaphors do not use words "like" or "as". Used metaphors have an explicit comparison between two different things. It is used for poetic or dramatic effect.

Figurative meanings are often culturally determined, and this can be problem for the translator. The figurative language we use stems from the underlying values and assumptions of our culture or society, so that a common metaphor in one culture may not be understood by people from other culture. For example, Shakespeare's *Romeo and Juliet*,

when Romeo famously says 'Juliet is the sun' some of the qualities of the sun (warmth, radiance, etc.) are transferred to Juliet. [11,15]. However, in Uzbek the sun has been defined as being 'hot, light, shining, bright, important' which is the same in English where Navoi delicately uses this comparison towards Nizami.

The metaphor 'He is the sun in the sky' means that the person is being talked is the light in one's life. Since the earth revolves around the sun, this phrase can mean that a person's life revolves around the person to whom he gave the compliment. As a literary symbol, it can represent a hero, knowledge, divinity, life force, brightness and overall splendor.

Another type of figurative language device simile also used to describe the essence of the word in the language and speech. He says: "The soul of the human is like a river and the word is like the pearl in it. Wise speaking man is as the diver who is going to pick pearls (words) under river (soul). Here the soul-river, word-pearl, wise speaking man-diver. The comparison is done on unlike words. As pearls are different, the words are different too. Pleasant and soft words prolong one's life, but evil word even kills human.

Similes embody associative poetical cognition of the object world based on the author's subjective-evaluative perception of the world and his/her individual gift for metaphorical mapping. Accordingly, we define the linguistic status of a simile as that of a language-in-use, i.e., textual construct of pragmatic nature in which the target object is metaphorically determined via comparing it with another, heterogeneous object, fixed as an image in the speaker's/writer's consciousness

In the epic poem "Farhod and Shirin" used similes to express the pragmatic nature of the described person or an object. In Uzbek the stylistic device simile (*o'xshatish*) has tenor (*o'xshatish subyekti*), vehicle (*o'xshatish etaloni*), ground (*o'xshatish asosi*) and lexical and grammatical indicators (*o'xshatish vositalari* -day, -dek, -simon, -larcha, -chasiga, -asiga, -omuz, -ona, -ga kabi qo'shimchalar: misoli, bamisoli, xuddi, singari, o'xshab, go'yo, go'yoki, qadar, aynan kabi so'zlar) as there are no *as* many in English as in Uzbek [16,71]. In English tenor and vehicle of simile which are united by formal markers: *as*, *as ...as*, *like*, *as though*, *as if*, *such as*. In translation of these markers the translator uses the most suitable equivalents of the target word. The marker "*as*" is used when it is followed with subject and predicate. For

example, Do everything as I do. (Xuddi mendek bajaring).

Another marker "like" is used when it is followed by the noun or noun phrase. For example, The small was like a fresh bread (Buning hidi xuddi yangi uzilgan nondek).

The structure "as...as" is used to compare things that are of similar proportion. In this case the first as acts as an adverb modifying the adjective or adverb that goes after it. The second as can act as a preposition or conjunction. If it is used as a preposition, it will be followed by a noun or pronoun. If it is used as a conjunction, it will be followed by a clause. For example: He is as cunning as a fox. (Here the first as in this construction modifies the adjective cunning. The second as modifies the noun fox.)

Analysis

Translating similes from one language to another can be challenging because they often rely on cultural references and idiomatic expressions that may not have direct equivalents. Here some general strategies for translating similes into Uzbek. The resulting translations might not convey the exact same meaning or impact as the original similes.

Replacing the comparison with a similar Uzbek simile: Try to find a simile in Uzbek that conveys a similar meaning or uses comparable imagery. This approach helps to maintain the figurative language and impact of the original simile. For example, if the English simile is "as busy as a bee", the translator could translate it into Uzbek as "asalaridek, chumolidek serharakat" (as busy as a bee or an ant).

Using descriptive language: Instead of relying on a direct simile, the translator can describe the qualities or actions being compared in terms that are more literal. This approach allows you to convey the intended meaning without using a specific simile. For instance, if the English simile is "as light as a feather" the translator could translate it into Uzbek as "paxtadek yengil" (as light as a cotton).

Modifying the structure: In some cases, it may be necessary to rephrase the simile entirely to match the linguistic structure and cultural context of Uzbek. This approach might involve using different sentence constructions or idiomatic expressions.

Explaining the intended meaning: If a simile does not have a direct translation or equivalent in Uzbek, you can opt to explain the intended meaning instead. This approach is particularly useful when the cultural or contextual references in the original simile

might not be familiar to Uzbek speakers. By providing an explanation, you can ensure that the intended comparison is understood.

We should mention that these are the general strategies, and the best translation will depend on the specific simile and its context.

Here we will analyze the translations taken "Farhod and Shirin" by Azam Abidov.

The translator uses all those mentioned techniques when translating simile to deliver the message of Navoi to the English readers. For example in the following sentence the first mentioned technique Replacing the comparison with a similar Uzbek simile was used.

Ko'pgina gavharlarning rangi ko'zga la'lga o'xshab qizil bo'lib ko'rinadi, qo'lga olganda esa cho'g' bo'lib chiqdi.[1,20]

Translation:

As vast majority of diamonds take on the cast of red, like a ruby, only to find upon taking them in your arms it merely a worthless cinder. [1,12]

Yig'laganda ko'zidan to'kilgan yoshlar har tarafga gavhar bo'lib sochilar, ko'z oldida shu gavhardek bir yosh go'dakning paydo bo'lishini istardi [1,21]

Translation:

When he wept, tears flowed like diamonds. He only wished that a newborn son would appear to him among those gems.

However, in the above given example the translator used Modifying the structure technique to give the full meaning of the sentence given in the source text.

In English, we use a large number of idiomatic expressions with as...as.

For example: Her hands were as cold as ice.

These stories are as old as the hills.

In Uzbek we also have great number of fixed idioms or phrase used in literary and common literary language. For example: tarashadek qotib qolmoq, bo'ridek och, suvdek tiniq, quyoshdek porloq, tulkiday ayyor, itdak charchamoq and so on. When translating these kind of idioms the translator faces with some challenges as this is based on cultural references and idiomatic expressions that may not have direct equivalents in the target language .

Conclusion

In conclusion, translating similes from one language to another, such as from Uzbek to English, can be a challenging task. Similes often rely on cultural references and idiomatic expressions that may not have direct

equivalents in the target language. However, by employing various strategies, it is possible to convey the intended meaning and preserve the figurative language of the original simile.

One approach is to search for comparable similes in the target language that convey a similar meaning or use similar imagery. This allows for the retention of the figurative impact of the original simile. Additionally, descriptive language can be used to explain the qualities or actions being compared in more literal terms, providing an alternative to direct similes. Adapting the structure and phrasing of the simile to match the linguistic and cultural context of the target language is another effective strategy. In cases where a simile lacks a direct translation or equivalent, explaining the intended meaning can be a suitable option.

tasvirlash, uning ruhiy holatini ochib berish, hayoti davomidagi qayg'u-iztiroblarining barcha nuqtalarini bera olishidadir.

XX asr boshlarida Zigmund Freyd va Karl Gustav Yunglar inson psixologiyasining asoslarini ishlab chiqishi bilan badiiy adabiyotda qahramon psixologiyasini o'rganish dolzarb ekanligini ko'rsatdi. Enraytning asarlarida ushbu psixoanalitiklarning mezonlariga asoslanib psixologik tahlil nuqtai nazari bilan yondashamiz. Ushbu tahlilda uning ikki romani – "What Are You Like?" va "The Gathering" hamda "Making Babies" esselar to'plamidagi onalik, til va o'zlikni anglash mavzulari ochib beriladi.

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